

**The Clash of Two Languages and their Battle for Supremacy: Implications
for the Teaching of English Language in a Creole Speaking Environment. A
Mini-Study.**

By Yonae Donald

Abstract. The battle has been raging for years. However, this sort of combat is not being fought on a literal battle ground but a psychological one. It is the battle of two languages- the Jamaican Creole and the Jamaican Standard English within the context of the English Language classroom. The paper highlights the critical role of the teacher in orchestrating an environment where both languages can coexist without the demise of the other. It examines the need for teachers to develop language awareness and to engage in professional development through research on theories applicable to developing language competence in the Jamaican language context. Hence, the purpose of this study is to examine the impact of the complex nature of the language situation on English language classrooms through the lens of an observed English language session at a non- traditional high school in rural Jamaica. It also seeks to analyze the extent to which this teacher of English successfully navigates such challenges to develop English language competence in her students.

Introduction and Background

The battle lines have been drawn. The scene is now set for an epic encounter to unfold. Two contending Factions are poised for a dramatic finale. The war cries are heard. The combat is fierce, claiming casualties. But in the end, one faction emerges as the victor. There have been many skirmishes of this nature in mankind's history, but many come to their end after a decisive show-down. However, the nature of the battle examined in this paper stands in sharp contrast. The characters and scenes might have changed but it has been perpetuated for centuries. The nature of the conflict is not physical but rather psychological. Today, it is played out in the social and political arenas and reenacted in English language classrooms. It is the battle of two languages: the Jamaican Creole and Standard Jamaican English, and their pursuit for supremacy in the English language classroom.

The language situation in the Jamaican context is a complex one. Unlike many other language environments where two languages coexist, are both recognized as prestige languages and share no similarities, the language situation in Jamaica differs sharply. In the Jamaican context, both languages are intricately woven as the Jamaican Creole is English based or derived. On the one hand, they share similarity in lexicon, but on the other end of the spectrum there are phonological, syntactical, and morphological differences. (Bryan 2004, 2010; Craig, 1983; Curtis, K., Williams, W., & Riddell. C, 2011; Davids, M. P,2013). For English language classrooms, this complexity forms the crux of the problem and augments the challenge of developing non- English speakers into competent English speakers and writers. Juxtaposed to this, is the challenge created by the diverse linguistic backgrounds of learners. Some enter the

education system as monolingual speakers; either of Jamaican Creole or Standard English, as bilingual; speakers of both languages or a variation of both (Bryan 2004, 2010).

The complex nature of the language situation in Jamaica has proliferated much of the unfounded beliefs and prejudices toward both languages. Much of these biases find their roots in the colonial past. The Jamaican Creole and Jamaican Standard English has shared an antagonistic past, as English as a language has been associated with oppression and the language of advancement. Creole has taken on a negative linguistic connotation as a deformed representation of the pure language, a failed attempt to speak English and has connotes inferiority (Bryan 2004,2010; Christie ,2003 as cited by Kuck ,2016; Davids ,2013 Klimova,2007; Prato, 2016; Siegel, 2006 as cited Åberg& Waller,2012). The disdain for creole is reflected in a statement made in the early post-colonial era. The creole speakers were referred to as "...speaking this sort of broken English, with an indolent drawling out their words, that is very disgusting if not tiring" (D'Costa and Lalla 1989 pp.15, as cited in Bryan, 2010 .pp.17) . This linguistic prejudice has persisted unchecked for centuries and the psychological chains of the past haunt us today as it permeates all sectors of the society. The psychological link to the past has shackled many misguided individuals in the education system as they attempt to 'purge' creole speakers of their native language, accentuating the Standard English as the 'pure' language, through the insistence that children 'speak properly'. This has only exacerbated the problem. The battle lines have been drawn and creole speakers have perceived this move as "subtle linguistic imperialism" (Deklerk, 1996 as quoted by kuck,2016, pp. 3) , a hostile tactic aimed at assaulting their identity; their very being. This has perpetuated feelings of contempt for Standard Jamaican English as its very existence ignites feeling of inferiority and inflicts linguistic scars in non-speakers (Davids, 2013). Kuck (2016) along with Aberg& Waller (2012) assert that language is a part of who we

are. Thus, speakers construct their identity through the use of language. Hence, from a historical perspective, rejection of Standard Jamaican English by non-speakers is a rebellion against years of psychological oppression.

The role of the Language teacher in this psychological warfare is critical. Being bilingual, the language teacher's role is twofold. First, it is the language teachers' role to initiate children into the culture of the school language (Bryan 2010). Second, while undertaking the aforementioned feat, the language teacher must skillfully maneuver through the hostile and complex language environment, to create an oasis where both languages can co-exist, without the demise of the other.

In view of the foregoing, the purpose of this paper is to examine the impact of the complex nature of the language situation on English language classrooms and to analyze the extent to which teachers are adequately addressing such challenges to develop English Language competence. This paper also seeks to address two key questions:

1. To what extent have language teachers developed critical language awareness themselves and in their students?
2. To what extent are language teachers' practice underpinned by knowledge and application of theories on transitioning creole speakers into competent English language speakers and writers.

Literature Review

The first step in beginning to address the challenge presented by the complex nature of Jamaicans' language situation is that of the language teacher developing language awareness. (Allsopp & Jennings, 2014; Bryan 2010, Craig 2006) He or she must recognize and acknowledge five essential truths: one, that Jamaican Creole is a language and is not a mere shadow or deformed representation of Standard English, hence, that there are two separate codes or languages operating in the Jamaican context, two: both languages are equal, three: the first language of most students is Jamaican creole (Bielanski & Speicher, 2000 ; Craig 1983;.) and as such students have a right to their mother tongue, like any other human right (Craig, 2006). Hence, it is imperative that language teachers purge themselves of any biases they might display toward Jamaican creole and begin to see it not a barrier to learning Standard English but as a gateway to it. Why are the aforementioned points critical? Developing language awareness on the part of the language teacher and creating an environment where the two languages are projected on equal standing, inhibits feelings of discrimination and inferiority on the part of creole speakers and engenders a spirit of respect for Standard English.

Krashen's affective filter hypothesis has a direct bearing on this first step. How? Krashen posits that the affective filter or screen manifests itself during language acquisition and is influenced by emotional variables that can prevent learning. The filter is raised if the learning environment makes students stressed, demotivated and are anxious. But the filter is lowered if the converse occurs (Abukhattala, 2013) In other words, if students feel demotivated and stressed because language teachers lack language awareness and promote Standard English as the language of prestige and Jamaican Creole is as a deformed representation of Standard English, the filter will

be raised and no language acquisition will take place. But if teachers recognize the two as distinct codes and projected them equals, then then filter will be lowered, and students will be more receptive to the target language.

The next step is developing language awareness in students. Beverly Bryan and Dennis Craig are staunch advocates of language awareness as an essential step towards acquiring the target language. Language awareness is the learner's ability to notice language, taking note of its form or contour, its function and role, being able to manipulate it to express him or herself, to use it understand the world around him or her (Bryan, 2010). In the Jamaican language context, awareness is critical as many learners have the misconception that because of the close similarity between the two languages then they are somehow homogeneous. Hence, some conclude that they already know English and so there is no need to learn the language. Noticing, recognizing, and separating the two languages as distinct codes is critical and is the first step towards acquiring the target language.

In order to develop language awareness in students, teachers must recognize their role in this process. It is crucial at this point to draw on Vygotsky's zone of proximal development theory. According to this theory there are three zones; what the learner knows, what the learner can do with assistance and what is out the reach of the learner cognitively. The theory proports that through social interactions with more knowledgeable others, children learn. A notable knowledgeable other is the teacher. Bryan (2010) emphasizes the critical role of teachers in this process. Bryan reinforced that the language teacher is the bridge between the two cultures, because being bilingual he or she knows the two languages: the language of the children's community and the school language or target language. It is the language teachers' role to initiate children into the culture of the school language. There is usually a disjuncture between the

language of home and that of school and the teacher is that link to bridge the gap between what the students know, their native language-creole, to what they need to know, the standard English. Bryan (2010) also proports that to bridge the gap students must be motivated. This school of thought encourages the full utilization of the learner's natural cultural environment to transition the learner from the known to the unknown. Using culture is a powerful tool as it provides a rich avenue for content through which learners can be immersed in the target language.

Immersion as defined in this context does not translate to the exclusive use of standard English, as this is not feasible in the Jamaican language context. Rather it involves increasing the input or exposure of learners to the target language. Hence, the teacher must create a language rich classroom and the language teacher must lead by example by modeling the language, seeing herself or himself as a critical source of input.

Another important way to immerse students in the target language and develop language awareness is through the use of technology. "Computer based e-learning is premised on new forms of interactivity as images, animation, colour and visual design interact with language in web-based communication.... provides new avenues for target language input, with the possibility too of objectifying language and increasing consciousness of its forms –noticing the item and registering its existence" (Bryan, 2010, pg. 108)

However, students must do more than develop language awareness. Through scaffolding, students have to be helped to make the transition from the language awareness to target language development. Craig has much to add to the literature in this regard. Craig (2006) advocates for the creation of a syllabus with a tailored programme to progressively transition students from the

first language to the target language. Such a programme facilitates continuity of cognitive growth. Placing non –English speakers in an environment hostile to their target language and demanding the exclusive use of English will inhibit cognitive development in that language. However, if creole speakers are allowed to use their language concomitantly with the target language, then cognitive growth would continue in the native language and could be transferable to target language through scaffolding or guided teaching. Hence, Craig advances that schools initially employ the full utilization of the learners’ native language. The rationale behind accommodation is that the first language will be used as a platform to facilitate target language development. As learners develop critical language awareness and their level of cognitive development parallels that of the native language then there would be a switch to full immersion in standard English.

Craig proposes the following method to achieve this. First, he suggests that initially native language speakers be allowed to use the vernacular in with peers and teacher in English language classrooms. Then, there should be time tabled sessions for the sole development of standard English. There should also be sessions allocated for what he terms as ‘free talk’. In these sessions students are allowed to use the vernacular to voice issues which affect them. The content from the ‘free talk’ is then used as input for language classes and form the basis for creating structured English sentences, “practice in English discourse as well as listening to and writing in English”(Craig, 2006,pp 39). This ‘free talk’ session should continue until the learners’ cognitive level and ability in the target language parallels that of the first language.

Closely connected to this approach is Craig’s augmented language experience approach. The language experience approach is centered around a learner generated text. The rationale underpinning this approach is to use content materials with familiar vocabulary and ideas as

these are more meaningful and more accessible than texts found in pre-prepared books. This approach recognizes and utilizes the cultural background of learners to develop English language competence. Using this approach, the teacher begins with the known by inviting students to use the vernacular to relate a cultural experience. The students' expressions are transcribed on the board by the teacher. The teacher then writes sentences in English mirroring the essence of the creole sentences, using simple grammatical structures and vocabulary which the learner can easily absorb but is not able to reproduce at that stage. The teacher models the language by reading the English sentences and the students then follow. The teacher will then use this avenue to draw attention to differences in grammar, phonology, and vocabulary between the languages. Here the process of noticing begins, and the learner begins to develop language awareness. Later to develop language competence though, the teacher keeps the tasks one step ahead of the learners' linguistic competence and supports learners' progress through scaffolding. As learners develop greater language autonomy the tasks increase in complexity. This approach draws on the principle of Krashen's input hypothesis and Vygotsky zone of proximal development theory (Abukhattala 2013; Turuk, 2008)

Another approach for transitioning learners from the first language to second language acquisition is that of using guided writing and speech, creative writing and speech as well as listening (including listening with viewing) activities. For this approach Craig (2006) highlights that listening is one of the most critical skill to develop as it provides comprehensible input for learners of the target language. It also allows learners to develop language awareness as it provides a medium through which the languages can be contrasted and it allows for the "initial reception of English element to be practiced and used" (Craig 2006, pp.50). As it relates to guided speech and writing in the target language, the teacher would orchestrate the context or set

the parameters for students to use the language. Students would therefore be restricted to using specific language forms. However, for creative speech and writing, students would be allowed within the constraints of context to freely express themselves using any language element they choose, from the repertoire they have learned.

Bryan (2004,2010) likewise speaks to the need to transition students from the native language to target language. She calls for teachers to provide students with opportunities for output through practice in using the language meaningfully. For many learners, there is a disconnect between the school context and real life. Language teachers must recognize that language is a lived experience. It is dynamic and in constant motion. Consequently, Language teacher regularly need to create for learners, varied opportunities to use the language in real life contexts.

Observation Site Background and Data Collection Instrument

Research Site: The observation was conducted at a rural non-traditional high school in Jamaica with a school population of 1648.

Ethical Considerations and Access to Site: The observer wrote a letter requesting permission from the principal of the institution to be granted access to the site for the lesson to be observed and recorded. The teacher of the class to be observed was approached prior to the observation and verbal permission was given to both observe and record the class session. Subsequent to the class observation, the teacher also agreed verbally to a recorded telephone interview.

Profile of Students: The predominant first language of the students is Jamaican Creole. The majority of the students are slow learners and entered the institution with averages below fifty in the core subjects.

Data Collection: For the purpose of this research, the researcher employed two methods of data collection. The first method involved an observation of a thirty minutes' observation of an English Language class in session. The second method was that of a recorded telephone interview with the teacher of the class which was observed. The rationale behind expanding the method of data collection to include an interview was that after desegregating the lesson observed, the findings necessitated further probing and exploration to ascertain the teacher's understanding of the complex nature Jamaican language context, the challenges which this presents and the theories which informed her practice.

For this section of the paper the researcher will engage in a reflection which includes an analysis of the findings from the observation and the interview. The report will be followed by a section focusing on recommendations based on of the findings.

Analysis of Data and Reflection

The class observed consisted of 25 students, 18 females and 7 males. The atmosphere during the session was a relaxed one. The students felt no inhibitions throughout the class in freely engaging in discussions with each other as well as with the teacher, using the vernacular. The students used the vernacular for 90% of the lesson. The vernacular was used to ask and respond to questions, for interaction between the peers and for expressing personal experiences, some relating to the lesson and others relating to personal matters. For this lesson, the students did not feel that the teacher was judgmental of their language background and so felt comfortable expressing themselves in the vernacular. This aspect of the lesson embodied the principle of Steven Krashen's affective filter hypothesis. This theory proports that a person's emotional and physical state can impede or promote learning. If the atmosphere is tense because students feel anxious or stresses, then the filter would be raised. However as if the atmosphere is a relaxed one and students do not feel threatened then this should promote learning.

There were only five occasions where the standard English was used by the students. These included reading of class material in the target language, for responding to an instruction from the teacher and for posing a question to the teacher. Throughout the lesson the teacher endeavored to model the English language, making effort to pronounce words using the English phonemic system. Bryan (2010) speaks to the critical role input plays in developing language awareness in students. This kind of input enables students to notice the contours of the target language. This would enable them to see the two languages as distinct codes. This is a crucial

step towards language awareness and development for target language competence. For example, on one occasion the teacher corrected a female student who used the creole phonetic system to pronounce the English word 'healthy'. However, instead of chiding the student, the teacher simply modelled the English pronunciation to highlight the contrast in pronunciation between the languages.

However, the teacher did not consistently model the target language throughout the lesson as she code switched in a few instances. The creole was used in one case to reprimand a student. For example, when there was an issue between two male students, the teacher's response was "com aafa Sheldan kies no!" In other instances, she moved from the acrolectal stage of the language continuum to the mesolectal stage unconsciously.

The researcher has noted that in many English language classrooms the use of the Jamaican Creole is not tolerated. The researcher wanted to probe into the teacher's rationale for accommodating Creole in the English language class and to ascertain whether this practice was underpinned by theory. Hence, in discussions with the teacher in a subsequent interview, the researcher posed these questions to the teacher. The teacher related that she saw the creole as an interference or hindrance to learning the language but believed that it was convenient to make allocations for the use of the vernacular in English classes so that students could express themselves in the language, they were competent in. Furthermore, in rare cases the creole language was used as a point of reference for contrasting with the standard English. However, there is no research which supports the notion that using Jamaican Creole will interfere with or hinder students' acquisition of standard English. On the contrary, research has proven that students who are taught both languages and who become bilingual, increase their ability to produce Jamaican standard English and perform better than monolingual students in general.

academics (Siegel, 2006, as cited in Alberg & Waller 2012; Simmonds-McDonald, 2004)

Furthermore, what does the literature say on the rationale for accommodation? Bryan

(2004, 2010) and Craig (2006) are advocates of employing the accommodation approach.

However, it must be purposive. The main purpose of accommodating the use of the vernacular in the target language class, is to bridge the gap between the two languages, using the first language as a platform for second language acquisition. Hence, the creole should not be seen as a barrier to second language acquisition but as a gateway to it. This is the misconception of many language teachers who see themselves as guardians of the English language. Instead, they should see themselves in the role of mediators between the languages.

The topic observed for the session was, Summary Writing. The lesson began with the teacher presenting students with a photocopied passage based on a CSEC past paper. The objectives of the lesson were not written or explained to the students, and this is where the lesson fell short.

Castek, Coiro, Donald, Henry, & Kenzer, (2013) defines learners today as ‘digital natives’, and as such technology could have been used to make the lesson more engaging for all students.

The students could have been placed in groups and asked to research the topic. They could present their summarized findings using the multi-media format and could have included graphics for visual and aural effect.

The lesson preceded with a male student being asked to read the instructions on the document.

This was followed by the teacher endeavoring to use simple language to explain the instructions as well as to clarify unfamiliar concepts. For example, the phrase ‘explicitly stated’ was used and the teacher used expressions such as “you have to figure out” or “it is not directly stated to explain the expression. In another instance, the teacher said “.... this is the crux of the matter....” And a confused male student asked “...the crux of the matter miss?” The word crux

was outside of the student's experience and the teacher paraphrased to simplify the word and the explanation was understood. It is unclear however, based on the linguistic and cognitive level of most of the students if they were able to process so much information at once. The content chosen for this lesson was beyond the cognitive level of most of the students and hence the students would require scaffolding and further cognitive development in the target language for a task of this magnitude. This might have explained why so few of them participated in the lesson. Krashen's input and natural order hypotheses, Vygotsky's zone of proximal development as well as Craig's augmented language approach emphasize the need for scaffolding, as student attempting to learn a new language will develop language skills and competence in stages. The content which forms the basis for lessons must be one step ahead of the learners' linguistic and cognitive level so as to move them along the continuum. The teachers' role, therefore, is to scaffold learners based on their linguistic and cognitive needs. This process should continue until the learner's cognitive development in the target language parallels that of the first language (Craig, 2006). Applying this approach could have resulted in better learning outcome.

While it is commendable that the teacher modelled the language, Bryan (2010) highlights the need for orchestrating real-life opportunities for output. Near to the conclusion of the lesson the teacher spoke to the matter of dementia as a consequence of not maintaining a healthy brain. One vocal female student, who was noted to consistently use the vernacular simply because she was allowed to, showed here ability to code switch when the occasion necessitated. Below are her expressions:

Female student A: A chuu mis, mi gran -fadda avi.

Teacher : Alzheimer ?

Female student A: Mis wan a dem. An sometime wen wi taak tu im ,im rimemba.

Wen mi nekz sista did go to im an se “a uu yu bi, a uu yu bi?”

An wen mi go tu im an im se “oh I remember you!”

An mi afi taak to im an se: “ oh,its Alesha”

When the student took on the persona of the grandfather who speaks the English language, she displayed the ability to model the language. Bryan (2004,2010) along with Curtis, K., Riddell, A., & Walson- Williams, C. (2011) call for teachers to provide students with opportunities for output through practice in using the language meaningfully. For many learners, there is a disconnect between the school context and real life. Language teachers must recognize that language is a lived experience. Language is not static. Consequently, Language teachers regularly need to create for learners, varied opportunities to use the language in real contexts.

In conclusion, based the lesson observed, the critical question which many would pose at this juncture is: did the use of the vernacular hinder development of the target language? However, the researcher believes that the question should be: Was the creole used as a platform for the development of English language competence? The answer for this question lies in the expressions of the teacher regarding her knowledge of theoretical methods used to transition creole speakers from their first language to the target language:

Teacher: “well we don’t get there yet. I really need to be able do that and that is where my limitations come in because I would need help where that is concerned. Because sometimes I am there scratching my heard wondering how do I take them to the next level.... I am not au fait with the theories “

Conclusion and Recommendations

In conclusion, one popular dictum used in the educational sphere is: “Theory without practice is for geniuses, practice without theory is for...villains, but for most educators there is a profound indissoluble union of both.” This underscores the critical role of theory in informing practice. Language teachers must be guided by an underlining philosophy, grounded in theory. Also, while it is commendable that an effort was made in the lesson to accommodate the students’ native language, the teacher was still tainted by a negative view of the creole, seeing it as an interference or hindrance for target language development. Teachers need to purge themselves of any trace of prejudice towards the language and see it as a bridge or gateway to target language development. The experience emphasizes the need for ongoing professional development with the focus on research on new theories, especially regional ones targeting teaching English in creole speaking context. Unless teachers are knowledgeable about such matters then the battle of the languages will continue to be perpetuated and unfortunately there will be casualties. One reassuring point though, emerging from the interview, was the teacher’s acceptance of her inefficiencies and her willingness to develop professionally through research to cater to the language needs of her students.

Accomplishing the feat of creating an ideal language classroom is a daunting one and but it is not unattainable. First, for the teachers, there must be an awareness of the historical context which has shaped the Jamaican language environment. Second, there must be critical language awareness; a recognition of the two languages as distinct codes. Third, acceptance of creole as

the students' first language and recognition of the right to use the language. fourth, knowledge of the connection between first and second language acquisition and skillfully using such knowledge to create a platform for the acquisition of the English Language. Fifth, classroom practice must be underpinned by theories based on research on transitioning learners from first language to second language acquisition.

Reference

- Aberg, A., & Waller, J. (2012). English Language Teachers' Perception of their Role and Responsibility in three Secondary Schools in Jamaica. Retrieved from <https://muep.mau.se/bitstream/handle/2043/13434/Dissertation%20%C3%85berg%20&%20Waller%20FINAL.pdf>
- Abukhattala.I. (2013) *Krashen 's' Five Proposals on Language Learning: Are they valid in Libyan EFL Classes?* English Language Teaching. Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1076806.pdf>
- Allsopp, J., & Jennings, Z. (Eds). (2014). *Language Education in the Caribbean. Selected Articles by Dennis Craig*. Kingston, Jamaica: The University of the West Indies Press
- Bryan, B. (2010). *Between two Grammars. Research Practice for Language and Teaching in a Creole Environment*. Kingston, Jamaica: Ian Randle Publishers
- Bryan, B. (2004). Language and literacy in a Creole-speaking environment: A study of primary schools in Jamaica. Retrieved from <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ728345>
- Craig, D.R. (2006). *From Vernacular to Standard English. Teaching Language and Literacy to Language Students*. Kingston, Jamaica: Ian Randle publishers.

Craig, D.R. (1983) Teaching Standard English to Nonstandard Speakers: Some Methodological Issues.

Journal of Negro Education, 52(1), 65-74. Retrieved from <https://jstor.org/stable/2294749>

Castek, J., Coiro, J., Donald, J.L., Henry, A.L., & Kenzer, C.K. (2013). *New literacies: A dual-level*

theory of the changing nature of literacy, instruction and assessment. Retrieved from

https://litmedmod.ca/sites/default/files/pdf/leu-ew_literacies_a_dual_level_theory.pdf

Curtis, K., Riddell, A., & Walson- Williams, C. (2011, January). *Collaboration or Collision: A Tale of*

two Languages-Jamaican Creole and Jamaican Standard English. Retrieved from

[https://www.mona.uwi.edu/cop/consolidated-reply/collaboration-or-collision-tale-two-](https://www.mona.uwi.edu/cop/consolidated-reply/collaboration-or-collision-tale-two-languages-jamaican-creole-and-jamaican)

[languages-jamaican-creole-and-jamaican](https://www.mona.uwi.edu/cop/consolidated-reply/collaboration-or-collision-tale-two-languages-jamaican-creole-and-jamaican)

Davids, M.P. (2013, January). *Languages as socio- cultural capital in the context of contemporary*

linguistic Reality of Jamaica. Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED544157.pdf>

Jessica, R.B., & Speicher, B.L. (2000). Critical Thoughts on Teaching Standard English. *Curriculum*

Inquiry, 30 (2), 147-169. <https://doi.org/10.1111/0362-6784.00160>

Kuck.M .H.(2016) *The reception in Jamaica of Non-native speakers of Jamaican*. *Journal of*

Christianity and English Language Teaching. Retrieved from

<http://cook.biola.edu/static/media/downloads/ijc-elt-volume-3-article-1.pdf>

Klimova, Z. (2007). *English as a Language of Oppression*. Retrieved from

https://is.muni.cz/th/kvex.English_as_the_Language_Of_Oppression.pdf

Prato,F. (2016, January). *An Analysis of Jamaican Creole*. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/31237370>

Simmonds-McDonald, H. (2004) Trends in teaching standard varieties to creole and vernacular speakers. *Annual Review of Applied Linguistic*, 24, 187-208. DOI: 10.1017/S0267190504000133

Turuk.M.C.(2008). *The Relevance and implications of Vygotsky's Socio-cultural theory in the second language classroom*. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/285909111_

Appendix A
CLASSROOM OBSERVATION FORM A

Instructor: _____ Course Title/Section _____

Date: _____ Time _____

A. CLASS PLANNING AND ORGANIZATION

- Class objectives matched published course syllabus
- Sequence of course material is organized to facilitate student learning
- Classes begin and end on time
- The instructor uses class time effectively

Comments:

B. KNOWLEDGE AND PREPARATION

- The instructor is well prepared for classes
- The instructor is knowledgeable and current in the subject area
- The instructor explains concepts clearly

Comments:

C. LEARNING ENVIRONMENT

- The instructor creates a relaxed, non-threatening environment for learning
- The instructor creates an environment where both the students' native language and the target language are promoted as equal.

Comments:

C. TEACHING METHODS/STYLE

- The instructor's preparation style facilitates student learning
- The instructor's practice is underpinned by theories on second language acquisition.
- The method(s) of instruction is appropriate for the class objectives
- The instructor stimulates student thinking
- The instructor provides opportunity for student questions
- The instructor responds concisely and clearly to student questions
- The instructor encourages students to participate in class using their native language
- The instructor has a genuine interest in students and their cultural backgrounds.
- The instructor uses the vernacular as a platform for target language development.
- The instructor consistently models the target language.

Comments:

E. ASSESSMENT/FACILITATION OF LEARNING OUTCOMES

- The instructor accomplishes class or course objectives
- The instructor provides supplemental material that facilitates student learning

Comments:

E. SUMMARY

Strengths:

Areas for Improvement:

APPENDIX B
Transcription of Observation

Selected Section A (00:25- 4:06)

Teacher: The first. This was given a couple of years ago as a like a diagnostic to see where the students were.

Female student A: So wi mos do it miss?

Teacher: So we are at summary and we are looking at a type

Female student B: Dis piej mis?

Teacher: No man! The first page where you see section one. Section one.

Female student A: uno tap i naiz no

Female student B: di big big part

Teacher: It does not have to be big to be bold

Female student B: Yes, miss

Teacher: No

Male student A: It's highlighted

Teacher: Don't on dii computer when you see dii b and when you highlight dii thing it becomes darker than the rest of the text. So that is bold. Bold doesn't have to be big. Good morning miss. where yu coming from?

Student C: Outside

Teacher: A realize. A realize. That's where dii class is? I'm not smiling.

Student C: Was doing something

Teacher: Obviously it must be something. But you need to be at class on time. Alright, can we have it (the summary passage) read? The instructions are very important. Alright, go ahead. Go ahead.

Male student A: Read the following extract carefully and then write a summary in not more than 120 words and as far as possible in your own words. Your summary must be in continuous prose an in paragraph form. If this limit is exceeded only the first 120 words of your answer will be read.

Teacher: read

Male student A: Yeah. Read and assessed

Teacher: Alright

Male student A: In your answer, you will be assessed on how you identify the main idea and opinions in the extract, organize and express these ideas and opinions in your own words, use appropriate grammar, sentence structure vocabulary, spelling and punctuation.

Teacher: Alright, so you see all of that and the suggested time is for this one is forty minutes. For the entire paper is about two hours and ten minutes. So what we are going to focus on are the three things you are being tested on. You are not expected to write a summary now. You are not there yet. However, I want you to see what is required of you. First, you should be able to identify what? What does a say?

Male student A: di main idea

Teacher: Main ideas. So it is more than one.

Female student: opinions

Teacher: Opinions

Male student A: Opinions are things that people think

Teacher: Alright. Then after you have found the main ideas and the opinions, what are you going to do next? B tells you

Male student A: Organize these ideas and opinions I n your own words

Teacher: Alright. Now there is where the crux of the matter is

Male student A: The crux of the matter miss?

Teacher: Yes. This is the serious part of the summary. This is where students either fail or do well when it comes to expressing these main ideas in their own words. A lot of students simply rewrite the passage and that's not summarizing it.

Male student A: Wi fi rait out di main aidia dem an put den an an, an before an after.

Teacher: Well you're going to learn how to do it, so first we are going to find the main idea.

Selected Section B (14:53- 15:45)

Teacher: Now since we have found the topic sentence and we were looking at supporting sentences. What else? What are some of some of the other information we get about the brain in this paragraph?

Male student A: Improving your brain health can protect you from demesia, improve your memory and sharpen your concentration.

Teacher: So that last sentence that he is highlighting, what is that telling us?

Male student a: Improving your brain health can protect you from brain disease mis an increase yu memory miss

Teacher: So don't you think we need to know what this d word means? Dementia?

Female student B: Mis yu mean like amnesia ?

Teacher: Right but it is a more severe form

Selected Section C. (16:05-16-40)

Female student B: Mis!

Teacher: It is the brain cells that are dying

Female student B: Mis a siem suh mi go visit mi anti mis, an mi go there an wi si dong and shi se “ a ouu unu agen? An wi tel ar bout faiv taim.

Teacher: And you have to be patient with them because it’s just that they have no control

Female student A: A chuu mis, mi gran -fadda avi.

Teacher : Alzheimers ?

Female student A: Mis wan a dem. An sometime wen wi taak tu im ,im rimemba.

Wen mi nekz sista did go to im an se “a uu yu bi, a uu yu bi?”

An wen mi go tu im an im se “oh I remember you!”

An mi afi taak to im an se: “ oh,its Alesha”

APPENDIX C
CLASSROOM OBSERVATION FORM B
Students’ use of JC and JSE

	Number of times used to ask questions relating to lesson.	Number of times used to ask questions relating to other matters.	Number of times used to respond to questions posed by teacher.	Number of times used to respond to questions posed by peers:	Number of times used in interactions with peers	Number of times used for expressing personal /cultural experiences:
Students' use of the vernacular						
Students' use of the Jamaican Standard English						
Students' ability to code switch						

Teachers' Use of Jamaican Creole and Jamaican Standard English

	To ask questions	To respond to question	To teach content	To Reprimand	To encourage
Teacher's use of the Vernacular					
Teachers use of Standard Jamaican English					

APPENDIX D

Teacher's use of JC and JSE during lesson

APPENDIX E

Students' use of JC and JSE during lesson

APPENDIX F
Interview Questions

1. What is the language background of the students under your charge?
2. What is your view of the language background of these students?
3. What is your view on allowing students to use their native language in the English language classroom?
4. In view of the language background of your students, how do you go about developing English language competence?
5. What role does the first language of learners play in second language acquisition?
6. Which local and international theories guide your development of English language competence in the environment you operate?

Appendix G

Transcription of Interview

Interviewer: What is the language background of your students?

Interviewee: The language background of my students, hmm. Well are you speaking in terms of how well they spoke the language or what it is that they know?

Interviewer: As in are they coming from a Creole speaking background or from a background where they speak only the Standard Jamaican English or mixture of both?

Interviewee: ok, well I would say that they are coming from a predominantly creole speaking background. There are a few who do speak the standard English but for the most part, they are coming from a creole speaking background and in the class that is what they speak most of the time.

Interviewer: Ok, thank you. What place does their language background have in the English language classroom?

Interviewee: Well, creole has its place yes and they are very proficient in that language. However, it does interfere with their ability to express themselves in the standard English or the target language because they, the truth is I think as teacher we treat teaching English language as a second language but we are doing it along the premise that the students know English but they do not. So yes creole has its place and it has its place in the classroom because you can use it to make points of reference with similarities and differences in the target language but it does interfere with how they express themselves in the target language.

Interviewer: Alright thank you. So what is your view of allowing them to use the creole, their native language in the classroom?

Interviewee: Well, I do allow it because some children can't express themselves adequately otherwise so if I don't allow them to speak the creole then those students will never participate in terms of expressing him or herself in class and I try to make my class a class where students can talk so yes I do give them an opportunity to use it. However, I try to model the language, the target language and ask others for example, how could we say this in the standard language, standard English. You heard what she said, you understand what she said but how could we say this now since we have been practicing the language, how do you say what she just said. As much as possible, I try to do that. The truth is, I should do more.

Interviewer: To create more of a contrast?

Interviewee: Yes

Interviewer: So what other strategies do you use in view of the language background of the students, what other strategies apart from modeling do you use in your classroom? In view of the background.

Interviewee: Well I try to give them reading, reading materials in the language and where they have to read aloud, so yes modeling comes back again but, I let them for example when we were doing summary and there were several situations and or passages that were used and students had to read it and talk about what they understood. For example, main idea and so forth and some of the passages you find that because of the vocabulary. Some of them didn't really get what it was saying because of the limitations they have with the target language but, I do find that if I try to find simple passages that I know that they will understand and since they are interested in things they are interested in I find that they gravitate better towards these.

Interviewer: So you use their cultural background as well as

Interviewee: Right, that sort of a thing. Sometimes it's difficult to get them but sometimes I have to make up stuff.

Interviewer: So in terms of the simple passages you mean in terms of structure the sentences are simple.

Interviewee: Right, too technical I can tell you, you're going to have a difficulty. Complex or compound sentences are too technical for them. If those are used, then you lose them.

Interviewer: So how do you get them to the point where they can develop the understand then more technical sentences, how do you get them to that point?

Interviewee: Well, we don't get there yet. I really need to be able to do that and there is where my limitation come in because I would need help where that is concern because sometimes I'm wondering and scratching my head how do I take them to the next level.

Interviewer: Ok, so in view of that them, do you know of. Are you aware of the role that first language plays in second language acquisition?

Interviewee: The role that first language plays in language acquisition meaning if they know how their first language works and they can see similarities and so forth, it's better for them to grasp it the one you want them to learn?

Interviewer: Yes

Interviewee: Well we know it's important and it has its place but in terms of strategies to reach that end I don't think I'm au fait with that.

Interviewer: So in terms of the theories which speak to how to transition children from the first language to the second language those are things you need to do a little bit more research on?

Interviewee: Exactly, definitely ok.